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Research Article

IMPACT OF GLIMEPIRIDE AND SITAGLIPTIN ON C-REACTIVE PROTEIN IN OVERWEIGHT PATIENTS SUFFERING FROM TYPE-2 DIABETES

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Abstract:

Objectives: The purpose of this research work was to provide the comparison of anti-inflammatory impact of glimepiride and sitagliptin by calculating the C - reactive protein (CRP) in the overweight patients suffering from type-2 diabetic.

Methodology: This research work was carried out at Sheikh Zayed Hospital Rahim Yar khan from March to September 2020. A sum of 110 overweight patients suffering from type-2 diabetes were separated into 2 groups. We gave tablet sitagliptin 50.0mg to the patients of Group-A whereas the patients of Group-B received the tablet of glimepiride 2.0mg for a period of complete 12 weeks. We titrated the dose according to the level of blood sugar. Primary outcome was the measurement of the alterations in the CRP whereas secondary outcomes were the alterations in the body mass index, level of blood sugar, level of HbA1c, profile of lipids and CRP from the baseline in both groups with the utilization of SPSS V.20.

Results: After completion of 12 weeks of treatment, there was an increase in body weight of the patients of glimepiride group but there was slightly reduction in the patients of sitagliptin group, however the difference was not significant statistically ($P=0.070$). Although, patients of both groups were present with decrease in the levels of HbA1c and blood sugar but this difference was also insignificant ($P=0.590$ and $P=0.170$ respectively). However, there was an improvement in the lipid profile much significantly in the patients of sitagliptin as compared to the patients of glimepiride group as TC (Total Cholesterol) (-25.0 ± 32.50 vs $+1.50\pm 45.40$ $P=0.020$), TG (Triglycerides) (-19.0 ± 44.60 vs -1.80 ± 48.70 $P=0.0010$), LDL- cholesterol (-10.0 ± 22.40 vs -0.80 ± 18.70 $P=0.0010$) and HDL-cholesterol (-2.60 ± 6.20 vs 1.20 ± 5.20 $P=0.030$). Sitagliptin decreased the CRP significantly as compared to glimepiride (-2.30 ± 1.80 vs 0.80 ± 1.50 $P=0.0010$).

Conclusion: There was strong anti-inflammatory impact of sitagliptin marked by the decrease in the level of CRP as compared to glimepiride in the overweight patients of type-2 diabetes. It also had the advantageous impacts on the glycemic as well as lipid profiles.

Keywords: Anti-Inflammatory, Type-2 Diabetes, Lipid, C - Reactive Protein, Glimepiride, Sitagliptin.

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INTRODUCTION:

Inflammation performs very important role in the progression of the cardiovascular disorders in the patients of diabetes. CRP is the most important marker of inflammation in different cardiovascular complications. CRP not only detects the inflammation in the joints but it also identifies the inflammation's severity in different cardiovascular complications [1]. It is also one of the most important independent markers in cardiovascular complications. CRP is the main cause for the generation of the monocyte chemoattractant protein-1 by the endothelial cells, which results in increase of the expression of intracellular adhesion molecule-1 as well as vascular adhesion molecule-1. CRP also induces monocyte cells to discharge the pro-inflammatory cytokines which perform an important role in the pathogenesis of different cardiovascular complications. Different research works discovered the possible role of the CRP in evaluation of the fluctuations in profile of lipids in response to intake of diet. These research work pointed out that all these alterations normally depend upon the baseline concentration of CRP in the individuals [2].

There is an increase in the level of baseline CRP in the obese patients as compared to normal healthy controls. Sitagliptin has the capability to inhibit the enzyme DPP-4. Different research works have showed that sitagliptin can produce the anti-inflammatory impacts with the decrease in the CRP in the patients of diabetes as well as patients of other complications [3]. This research work aimed to determine the influence of sitagliptin and glimepiride on level of CRP in overweight patients suffering from type-2 diabetes.

METHODOLOGY:

We conducted this research work after taking the approval of Ethical Committee of the hospital. We took the written consent from all the patients after describing them the purpose of this research work. A sum of 450 patients of type-2 diabetes receiving oral antidiabetics were screened over the duration of this research work at Sheikh Zayed Hospital Rahim Yar Khan. From these, 110 patients got enrolment in the research work on the basis of inclusion criteria. 110 patients of type-2 diabetes having HbA1C level of less than 9, BMI greater than 25, getting glimepiride as oral antidiabetic agents were the participants of this research work. Patients suffering from other serious complications or other types of diabetes, females with

pregnancy or patients with BMI of more than 30 were not included in this research work. We divided the patients into two separate groups. The Group-A patients were switched from the antidiabetic of glimepiride 2.0mg to receive the oral sitagliptin of 50.0mg after wash period of 7 days for a period of complete 12 weeks whereas Group-B patients continued to take the tablets of glimepiride 2.0mg for the complete period of the research work. We calculated the BMI of the all the patients. Samples of blood were obtained after 12 hours fasting. We separated the serum after centrifugation and stored at a temperature of 4°C for complete 60 minutes until the time of analysis for CRP. We used the standard kit for the measurement of the CRP in all the samples. We used the oxidase method for the estimation of the blood sugar. We also used the enzymatic end point procedure and chromatography for the determination of the serum lipid and HbA1c levels respectively.

We calculated a sample size for the detection of the difference of the level of HbA1c over 0.50% with 90.0% power and 5.0% significance. We increased the size of samples to fifty-five patients per group for the accommodation of the anticipated rate of dropout. We used the SPSS V.20 for the statistical analysis of the collected information. We used the Fisher's exact test for the comparison of the non-parametric information in terms of gender and disease duration. We expressed the parametric data in terms of BMI, weight of body, blood sugar, and HbA1c and lipid profiles in averages and SDs from the baseline. We used the paired T test for the comparison. P value of less than 0.050 was considered as significant statistically. We used the unpaired t-test for the comparison of the patients of both groups after 12 weeks.

RESULTS:

Profile of tolerability and safety of both the drugs were much good in the duration of this research work. Out of 110 patients, 8 patients failed to complete the research work. There was development of hypoglycemia in 5 patients in the group of glimepirides whereas 3 patients in the group of sitagliptin failed to complete the follow-up in the duration of this research work. Overall, one hundred and two patients finished this research work, fifty-two patients in the group of glimepirides (Group-A) and fifty in group of sitagliptin (Group-B). Baseline demographic traits and data of laboratory of the patients of both groups is present in the Table-1.

Baseline Characteristics		Number of Patients (N=110)
Demographic Characteristics	Age (years) (mean $\pm$ SD)	54 $\pm$ 8
	Sex (male/female)	70(63.6%)/40(36.3%)
	BMI (kg/m ²) (mean $\pm$ SD)	27 $\pm$ 4
	Duration of Type-2 DM (years) (mean $\pm$ SD)	6.8 $\pm$ 2.5
Laboratory parameters (mean $\pm$ SD)	Fasting Blood glucose (mg/dl)	156 $\pm$ 10.5
	HbA1c (%)	7.9 $\pm$ 2.8
	Total Cholesterol (mg/dl)	192 $\pm$ 23.5
	Triglycerides (mg/dl)	187 $\pm$ 19.2
	LDL-Cholesterol (mg/dl)	120 $\pm$ 12.4
	HDL-Cholesterol (mg/dl)	41.3 $\pm$ 3.6
	hsCRP (mg/L)	5.8 $\pm$ 6.7

After the completion of treatment, although there was increase in the weight of body in Group-A, but there was slightly reduction in the patients of Group-B but the difference was not much significant ($P=0.070$). In the similar manner, comparison of the HbA1c and blood sugar of the patients of both groups showed insignificant results ($P=0.590$ and $P=0.170$ respectively).

Profile of lipid was improved in the patients of sitagliptin group as compared to the patients of

glicemipiride group i.e., TC (25.0 ± 32.50 vs $+1.50\pm 45.40$ $P=0.020$), TG (-19.0 ± 44.60 vs -1.80 ± 48.70 $P=0.0010$), LDL-cholesterol (10.0 ± 22.40 vs -0.80 ± 18.70 $P=0.0010$) and HDL-cholesterol (-2.60 ± 6.20 vs 1.20 ± 5.20 $P=0.030$). Sitagliptin also decreased the CRP in the patients as compared to the patients of glicemipiride group (-2.30 ± 1.80 vs 0.80 ± 1.50 $P=0.0010$). All these results are present in Table-2.

Table-II: Mean Changes of Study Parameters from Baseline in Both Study Groups

Parameters	Glicemipiride (N=52)	Sitagliptin (N=50)	P value
BMI (kg/m ²)	1.6	-0.02 $\pm$ 0.7	0.07
Fasting Blood glucose (mg/dl)	-35 $\pm$ 14.2	-27 $\pm$ 18.4	0.59
HbA1c (%)	-2.4 $\pm$ 4.8	-1.8 $\pm$ 5.2	0.17
Total Cholesterol (mg/dl)	+1.5 $\pm$ 45.4	-25 $\pm$ 32.5	0.02
Triglycerides (mg/dl)	-1.8 $\pm$ 48.7	-19 $\pm$ 44.6	0.001
LDL-Cholesterol (mg/dl)	-0.8 $\pm$ 18.7	-10 $\pm$ 22.4	0.04
HDL-Cholesterol (mg/dl)	1.2 $\pm$ 5.2	-2.6 $\pm$ 6.2	0.03
hsCRP (mg/L)	0.8 $\pm$ 1.5	-2.3 $\pm$ 1.8	0.001

DISCUSSION:

The manifestation of the inflammation is very difficult clinically. It is much crucial to identify the silent inflammation in obese as well as patients of diabetes and it can lead to high rate of morbidity as well as mortality [4]. This complication poses a heavy burden on health as well as economy. There are several inflammatory markers to identify the inflammation but

one of the most important markers is CRP [5,6]. It performs very vital role in the detection of the inflammation [7]. After completion of 12 weeks of treatment, sitagliptin decreased the inflammation with the significant decrease in the CRP. The CRP decrease was further accompanied by the improvement in the lipid profile and glycemic control without any effect on the weight of body [8]. Some research works

considered the sitagliptin as the safe and secure oral antidiabetic medicines [9]. This drug also has the beneficial effects on the profile of serum lipid. The findings of these research studies are similar with the results of this research work [10].

The findings about the primary objective of this research work about inflammation were comparable with the results of the research study conducted by Asahara who discovered that sitagliptin 50.0mg daily for a duration of complete 3 months not only improved lipid and glycemic profiles but also decreased the level of inflammatory markers like CRP & TNF- α in the patients suffering from type-2 diabetes [11,12]. Same results were also provided by the study conducted by Tremblay and his colleagues but the mentioned duration was 6 weeks. One other research work stated the improvement in the endothelial dysfunction with the use of sitagliptin [13]. One other research concluded that sitagliptin can decrease the IL-6 and CRP levels as well as it strengthens the anti-atherogenic properties in the patients. There is presence of some other research works which showed that although there was improvement in the hemodynamic and metabolic parameters in the patients of type-2 diabetes because of sitagliptin but it failed to improve the inflammation with the decrease of CRP [14]. There are some limitations of this research work as we ignore the other variables like TNF- α and different interleukins which can play important role in inflammation. There is need of further research works on large sample sizes to consolidate the findings of this research work.

CONCLUSION:

There is very strong anti-inflammatory influence of sitagliptin as marked by the decrease in the level of CRP as compared to glimepiride in the overweight patients of type-2 diabetes. It has advantageous influence on the lipid and glycemic profiles.

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